

Heterocyclic Compounds. Part VI. Synthesis of 1-Methyl-7-(1-ethyl-3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)indole

J. R. Merchant, D. D. Vaghani, and C. S. Kallianpur

The first-stage Hofmann degradation product from apoerysopine affords an indole derivative after reduction and subsequent dehydrogenation. The indole derivative has been synthesised by an application of the Madelung synthesis.

During the course of their studies on the structure of the Erythrina group of alkaloids, Folkers and his collaborators¹ studied the Hofmann degradation of apoerysopine (I). The first-stage Hofmann degradation product, *des*-methylapoerysotrine (II), obtained by us, was an oil instead of a crystalline solid (m.p. 72-73°), as described by the above authors. On catalytic reduction the oil, however, afforded a solid of m.p. 94-95° which was designated as dihydro-*des*-methylapoerysotrine (III). The latter on dehydrogenation over palladium-charcoal yielded a solid which from its absorption spectra and colour reaction with Ehrlich's reagent was identified as an indole derivative and assigned the structure 1-methyl-7-(1-ethyl-3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)indole (IV).

1. Folkers *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 591.

The present work describes the synthesis of compound (IV) by an application of the Madelung synthesis on 2-ethyl-2'-formamido-4,5-dimethoxy-3'-methylbiphenyl (followed by methylation) which was obtained by acylation of 2'-amino-2-ethyl-4,5-dimethoxy-3'-methylbiphenyl (VI). The latter was synthesised by reduction of 2-ethyl-4,5-dimethoxy-3'-methyl-2'-nitrobiphenyl (VII) which itself was prepared by the Ullmann reaction between 4-ethyl-5-iodoveratrol (VIII) and the known 3-bromo-2-nitrotoluene² (IX) in presence of copper powder.

4-Ethyl-5-iodoveratrol (VIII) was prepared by iodination of the known 4-ethylveratrol³ with iodine in ethanolic solution in presence of mercuric oxide. The position of iodine in (VIII) was established by oxidation with potassium permanganate to the known 5-iodoveratric acid⁴.

EXPERIMENTAL

Dihydro-dos-methylapoerysotrine (III).—Apoerysopino (500 mg.) was treated with dimethyl sulphate and 30% KOH solution, as described by Folkers *et al.*¹ The crude product of the Hofmann degradation was heated at 165-80°/0.001 mm to yield 430 mg. of a pale yellow oil which did not crystallise even after two months. A part of it was redistilled. $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 294, 264 m μ (log ϵ , 3.87, 4.21).

The remaining oil (410 mg.) was hydrogenated in methanol (25 ml) over platinum catalyst. Removal of the solvent left a colorless crystalline solid (398 mg.) which after crystallisation from cyclohexane, followed by sublimation under vacuum, melted at 96-97°. It developed a scarlet colour with ethanolic ferric chloride solution and was soluble in 5% HCl. (Found: C, 76.6; H, 7.6; N, 4.9; OMe, 19.8; N-Me, 4.6; C-Me, 3.3. C₁₉H₂₃O₂N requires C, 76.7; H, 7.8; N, 4.7; OMe, 20.9; N-Me, 5.1; C-Me, 5.0%). $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 288 m μ (log ϵ , 3.8).

Its *picriclone* after two crystallisations from ethanol had m.p. 169-71° (decomp.). (Found: C, 61.9; H, 5.7. C₂₉H₃₁O₇N₃ requires C, 62.0; H, 5.5%).

1-Methyl-7-(1-ethyl-3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)indole (IV).—An intimate mixture of compound (III) (25 mg.) and palladium on carbon (10%, 9 mg.) was placed in a glass tube from which the air was removed by adding pieces of dry ice. The tube was heated under vacuum at 275-80° for 1 hour when a colorless oil sublimed. The tube was sealed and kept aside when the oil solidified to colorless crystals. After crystallisation from methanol and sublimation under vacuum, it melted at 119-20°. (Found: C, 77.1; H, 7.16; N, 4.9. C₁₉H₂₁O₂N requires C, 77.3; H, 7.2; N, 4.7%). The compound is insoluble in 5% HCl and develops readily a deep magenta colour with the Ehrlich reagent. Its U.V. spectrum in ethanol is shown in Fig. 1 and I.R. spectrum in Fig. 2.

4-Ethyl-5-iodoveratrol (VIII).—A solution of 4-ethylveratrol (22.4 g.) in ethanol (60 ml) was stirred and treated alternately with iodine (37 g.) and yellow mercuric oxide (20.4 g.), added in small amounts during 1 hour. After stirring for another hour, the solution was filtered and the residue washed well with ethanol. Removal of the

2. Elson *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2741.

3. Berger and Silberschmidt, *ibid.*, 1928, 2926.

4. Raiford and Perry, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1942, 7, 354.

solvent left a dark oil which was extracted with ether. The ether solution was washed successively with sodium thiosulphate (20% solution), 2*N*-NaOH, and water.

FIG. 1. UV spectrum of compound (IV) in EtOH.

FIG. 2. IR of spectrum compound (IV).

Distillation of ether, after drying, yielded a solid (16 g.) which after two crystallisations from light petroleum had m.p. 58-59°. (Found: C, 41.3; H, 4.66. $C_{10}H_{13}O_2I$ requires C, 41.1; H, 4.5%).

Oxidation of (VIII) to 5-Iodooveratric Acid.—To a mixture of $KMnO_4$ (3g.) and $MgSO_4$ (2 g.) in water (53 ml) was added 4-ethyl-5-iodoveratrol (1 g.); the mixture was refluxed for 7 hours. After cooling, a current of SO_2 was passed through the solution and the white precipitate obtained was crystallised from methanol, m.p. 183-84°. Its m.p., when mixed with 5-iodoveratric, prepared according to Raiford and Perry⁴, showed no depression.

3-Bromo-2-nitrotoluene was prepared by a method analogous to that described for the preparation of 3-chloro-2-nitrotoluene⁵. The structure of the bromo compound was confirmed by its oxidation to the known 3-bromo-2-nitrobenzoic acid⁵.

5. Holleman, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1901, 20, 215.

2-Ethyl-4,5-dimethoxy-3'-methyl-2'-nitrobiphenyl (VII).—A mixture of 4-ethyl-5-iodoveratrol (2.2 g.) and 3-bromo-2-nitrotoluene (1.1 g.) was heated to 170° and copper powder (2.3 g.), previously washed with ether, was added with stirring in small amounts at a time during 10 minutes. The temperature of the mixture was gradually raised to 235-40° and kept there for an hour. The resulting brownish mass was extracted with hot ethanol (150 ml) and the solution boiled with animal charcoal. Removal of the solvent left a yellow solid (600 mg.) which after crystallisation from ligroin melted at 123-24°. (Found: C, 67.6; H, 5.85. $C_{17}H_{19}O_4N$ requires C, 67.76; H, 6.3%).

2'-Amino-2-ethyl-4,5-dimethoxy-3'-methylbiphenyl (VI).—The biphenyl (VII) (1.5 g.) was hydrogenated in ethanol solution in presence of Raney nickel. The solid obtained after removal of the solvent was crystallised from dilute methanol in white plates, m.p. 86-87°. (Found: N, 5.5. $C_{17}H_{21}O_2N$ requires N, 5.2%). Its picrate melted at 205-207°.

2-Ethyl-2'-formamido-4,5-dimethoxy-3'-methylbiphenyl (V) was obtained by heating the biphenyl (VI) with formic acid at 100° for 3 hours. The solid obtained after dilution with water was crystallised from benzene-light petroleum mixture, m.p. 152-59°. (Found: N, 5.0. $C_{18}H_{21}O_3N$ requires N, 4.7%).

7-(1-Ethyl-3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)indole.—The method described below is related to the Madelung synthesis of 2-alkylindoles⁶.

A three-necked r.b. flask (100 ml) was fitted with a reflux condenser and a glass inlet tube connected to a cylinder of nitrogen. The third opening of the flask was closed by a stopper. The top of the condenser was connected to an air trap which consisted of two 500-ml suction flasks joined in series. The first suction flask was kept empty; the second flask was filled with 100 ml of paraffin oil and the inlet tube of this flask was extended slightly below the surface of the oil.

In the reaction flask was placed anhydrous butanol¹ (15 ml) and the air in the flask was displaced by dry nitrogen gas. Metallic potassium (700 mg.) was added in portions to butanol¹. The mixture was heated on a water bath until all the potassium had dissolved and then the biphenyl (V) (800 mg.) was added to it. The condenser was set for distillation and the receiver was protected from the air by connecting it to the air trap used in the initial operation. The reaction flask was surrounded by a metal bath, and the excess of the alcohol was removed by distillation. The residue was heated to 350-60° for about 20 mins. and was allowed to cool in a stream of nitrogen. It was decomposed by addition of water (15 ml) and just acidified with HCl (dil.) with cooling. It was then extracted with ether. The ether layer was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Removal of the ether left a brown pasty solid (400 mg.), m.p. 90-130°. It developed a green colour with ferric chloride solution and a violet colour with the Ehrlich reagent. The coloration with ferric chloride indicated that demethylation had occurred during cyclisation.

A solution of the above solid (400 mg.) in acetone (100 ml) was refluxed for 12 hours with methyl iodide (850 mg.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (1 g.). After filtration and removal of the solvent, a brown oily residue was obtained. It was taken up in ether

6. Madelung, *Ber.*, 1912, 45, 1130; Tyson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 2024.

and washed with alkali (5%) and then with water. Distillation of the solvent yielded a brown pasty mass (380 mg.). It was dissolved in benzene and the solution passed over a column of neutral alumina (6 g.). On elution with benzene, a crystalline solid mixed with a little yellow oil was obtained. Two crystallisations from ethanol afforded needles (70 mg.), m.p. 164°. (Found: C, 76.2; H, 6.7; N, 5.2. $C_{18}H_{19}O_2N$ requires C, 76.8; H, 6.8; N, 5.0%). It gave a violet colour with the Ehrlich reagent. $\lambda_{\max}^{EtOH}$ 280 m μ (log ϵ , 4.1).

Methylation.—The above indole (50 mg.) was methylated according to the method described by Potts and Saxton⁷. It was obtained as a semisolid residue which after crystallisation from methanol had m.p. 117-18°. (Found: N, 4.9. $C_{19}H_{21}O_2N$ requires N, 4.7%). Its m.p. when mixed with (IV) showed no depression.

Thanks of the authors are due to Mr. W. Manser, Zürich, and Mr. R. S. Kulkarni for carrying out the micro-analyses.

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE, BOMBAY-1.

Received August 29, 1962.

